

Synthesis of Some Derivatives of *p*-Amino Butyl Benzoates and Terephthalanilide Analogues

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Some possible derivatives of *p*-amino iso-butyl and *n*-butyl benzoates have been synthesised to evaluate their local anaesthetic and spasmolytic activity. Some terephthalanilide analogues have been also prepared with a view to studying their therapeutic activity against leukaemia¹.

According to Einhorn² all the esters have capacity to produce anaesthesia. The least requirement for a compound to produce anaesthesia is that the compound must be ester of an aromatic acid. A number of derivatives of *p*-amino alkyl benzoates on testing have shown increasing potency as the length³ of alkyl group increases upto *n*-butyl group. Mattocks and Hutchinson⁴ suggested that compounds containing larger aromatic nucleus frequently possess greater activity than their benzene analogues. Taking these all into consideration some derivatives of *p*-amino butyl benzoates have been prepared. Keeping in view that some terephthalanilide derivatives⁵⁻⁶ have shown high order of therapeutic activity against leukaemia, few terephthalanilide analogues have been synthesised by condensation of terephthaloyl chloride with 2-ethyl indole and 4-hydrazino pyridine N-oxide in acetic acid medium for evaluating their therapeutic activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Amino *n*-butyl and iso-butyl benzoates were prepared by the method of Brill⁷ in 38% yield.

2'-Hydroxy benzylidene-4-Amino iso-butyl benzoate: A mixture of salicylaldehyde (1.3 gm.; 0.01 mole) and *p*-amino iso-butyl benzoate (2 gm; 0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol (10 ml.) was heated under reflux for 4-5 hrs. Excess of alcohol was removed under reduced pressure. A deep yellow mass was being separated which was filtered and washed with ether three times. Product on crystallisation with ethanol afforded analytical sample yield (3.0 gm.), m.p. 81°. Found: N, 4.50; C₁₈H₁₉NO₃ requires: N, 4.7%. The absorption bands characteristic of > C = N band at 1630 cm⁻¹ and > C = O at 1720 cm⁻¹ were found to be of high intensity.

2'-Hydroxy benzylidene-4-amino *n*-butyl benzoate: It was prepared by condensation of *p*-amino *n*-butyl benzoate (2.0 gm; 0.01 mole) and salicylaldehyde (1.3 gm; 0.01 mole)

1. H. F. Oettgen, P. Clifford and J. H. Burchenal, *Cancer Chemother. Rep.*, 1963, No. 27, 45.
2. Einhorn, *Ann.*, 1897, **296**, 328; **299**, 346.
3. Adams, Rideal, Burnett, Jenkins and Dreger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 1758.
4. Mattocks and Hutchinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3474.
5. S. A. Schepartz, I. Wodinsky and J. Leiter, *Cancer Chemother. Rep.*, 1962, No. 19, 1.
6. R. Hirt and R. Berchtold, *Cancer Chemother. Rep.*, 1962, No. 18, 5; *Experientia*, 1961, **17**, 418.
7. C. H. Brill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1320.

by the method described above in 80% yield, m.p. 79–80°. (Rep. 81°). Found : N, 5.0; $C_{18}H_{19}NO_3$ requires : N, 4.7%.

1-Phenyl-3-(p-iso-butyl) benzoate thiourea : *p*-Amino isobutyl benzoate (1.5 gm; .008 mole) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.0 gm; .008 mole) were dissolved in alcohol separately and mixed. The mixture was refluxed on water bath for 1 hr and cooled. White crystalline solid was separated which was filtered and washed with ether. Product on crystallisation with ethanol gave a sample, m.p. 202°, yield (2.0 gm) 75%. Found : N, 8.8; $C_{18}H_{20}N_2O_2S$ requires : N, 8.53%. The infrared spectrum showed an intense band in the carbonyl region at 1720 cm^{-1} and other at 1360 cm^{-1} due to $>C=S$ group.

4-Picryl amino iso-butyl benzoate : A mixture of Picryl chloride (1.2 gm; .005 mole) and *p*-Amino iso-butyl benzoate (1.0 gm; .005 mole), potassium carbonate (0.6 gm; .005 mole) were refluxed with absolute ethanol (10 ml.) for 2 hrs. The residue thus separated was filtered and washed with ether and water respectively. Crystallisation with ethanol gave an analytical sample m.p. 146°, yield (1.6 gm.) 80%. Found : N, 13.6; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4O_8$ requires : N, 13.86%. The infrared spectrum (KBr) of the compound showed two intense bands at 1700 cm^{-1} and 1610 cm^{-1} due to $>C=O$ and $>C-NO_2$ groups respectively. A medium band was also observed at 1180 cm^{-1} due to $-CH(CH_3)_2$ group.

4-Picrylamino n-butyl benzoate : It was prepared by *p*-amino *n*-butyl benzoate (2.0 gm; .005 mole), picryl chloride (2.4 gm; .005 mole) by the method described above, yield (1.8 gm) 88%, m.p. 159–60°. Found : N, 14.1; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4O_8$ requires : N, 13.86%.

4-(2-Pyridyl amino) acetyl amino iso-butyl benzoate : 4-Monochloroacetyl amino iso-butyl benzoate (1.0 gm; .005 mole) and 2-amino pyridine (0.7 gm; .008 mole) were refluxed with absolute ethanol (10 ml.) for 6 hrs. On cooling, yellow solid was being separated which was filtered and washed several times with water and ether. Crystallisation of the compound with ethanol afforded analytical sample, yield (1.0 gm.), m.p. 281–82°. Found : N, 13.3; $C_{18}H_{21}N_3O_3$ requires : N, 12.96%. Infrared spectrum (KBr) of the compound showed a strong band at 1700 cm^{-1} due to $>C=O$ group and a weak band at 3300 cm^{-1} due to secondary $-NH$ group.

1,1'-Terephthaloyl bis-(2-ethylindole) : The compound was prepared by refluxing terephthaloyl chloride (0.4 gm; .002 mole) and 2-ethylindole (0.6 gm; .004 mole) with glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) in presence of few drops of pyridine for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture on standing for 0.5 hr gave a white solid which was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%) and then with water and ether respectively. Compound on crystallisation with D.M.F. gave a pure sample m.p. $>300^\circ$, yield (0.3 gm.). Found : N, 6.8; $C_{23}H_{24}N_2O_2$ requires, N, 6.6%.

Phenyl 1,4 bis- γ -pyridyl N-oxide hydrazide : Terephthaloyl chloride (0.2 gm; .001 mole) and 4-hydrazino pyridine N-oxide (0.25 gm; .002 mole) were refluxed with glacial acetic acid for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture on cooling afforded a white solid which was filtered and washed with ethanol. Crystallisation with D.M.F. gave analytical sample, yield (0.2 gm.), m.p. $>300^\circ$. Found : N, 21.9; $C_{18}H_{16}N_6O_4$ requires, N, 22.1%.

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